

ENRICHMENT OF THE SYNONYMIC SERIES OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE DUE TO THE BORROWED WORDS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7205822>

During its many centuries of historical development, the Uzbek language enriched and improved its vocabulary at the expense of its internal sources. According to this law, new words were created because of their layers, the meanings of existing words were expanded, additional tasks were assigned to some words, the literary language was added to the literary language in folk dialects in different periods, according to the need, the words were accepted.

Internal sources are an important basis for the enrichment of the Uzbek vocabulary. However, just as no language in the world can rely on its own internal resources, the Uzbek language is not only dependent on its own words, its wealth and capabilities. External sources play an important role in enriching and improving the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. In general, any language cannot live in a pure state. It is legal for different languages to have certain relations with each other in different historical conditions. Such an attitude can leave certain traces in the development of the languages in contact, especially in its vocabulary. For this reason, two laws are observed that are common to changes in the vocabulary of all languages in the world, including the vocabulary of the Uzbek language:

- 1) replace the old with the new;
- 2) receiving words from other languages.

Therefore, the vocabulary of the Uzbek language relies on two sources in its development:

- a) Internal source;
- b) External source.

Therefore, the words in the lexicon of the Uzbek language do not go back genetically only to the lexicon of ancient Turkic tribal languages (common Turkic words). In addition to the words of its own layer, it also contains words adopted from other languages at different times.

The influence of other languages on the Uzbek language can be seen in two important cases:

1. Accepting foreign words into the Uzbek language.
2. Adapting foreign language words to the Uzbek language.

The introduction and assimilation of words from one language to another is not just a simple process, but a regularity associated with complex linguistic and socio-historical conditions. In order for words to be acquired from one language to another, there must first be a real situation. Such conditions are cooperation of languages, that is, communication between languages.

The current Uzbek language has historically experienced complex stages of development and formation. The Uzbek language was in contact with a number of sister languages, as well as foreign languages, during the periods of clan and tribal language, folk language, national language, and the language of the social nation.

The language of Turkic clans and tribes has been in contact with the Iranian languages that have lived in Central Asia since ancient times. The people who lived in Central Asia, including the territory of present-day Uzbekistan, spoke local language dialects belonging to the Iranian language group. This was the language of the Iranian clan - tribes, peoples - Sogds, Sakas, Massagets, Bactrians, Parthians, Parikanians, Khorezmians and others. In addition, in the ancient Kingdom of Bactria, the Greek language was used, as well as a language consisting of a mixture of Greek and Iranian languages.

In the territory of Central Asia, including present-day Uzbekistan, there was also an ancient Khorezm language, which had the characteristics of an Iranian language. There was a certain connection between this language and the local Turkic languages of that time. There is evidence in historical sources that shows that Khorezm writing was widespread in the VII-VIII centuries and before. It is known that in the 13th and 14th centuries, the inhabitants of Khorezm spoke two languages - Turkish and the ancient Khorezm language. The ancient Khorezm language was assimilated into the Uzbek language by the 14th century. As a result, some words related to this language have been preserved in modern Uzbek: xon (xob), bog, pochcha (picchomi-dadam), sky (osm), juft (er), ariq (ar -water) and others.

The Uzbek language has been in contact with a number of unrelated languages in the past. Such languages are Persian-Tajik and Arabic. In addition, the Uzbek language entered the period of its development as a national language and the

language of the social nation and entered into contact and cooperation with the Russian language, and this process continues.

The interaction and cooperation of languages often leads to the exchange of words between these languages, the transfer of words from one language to another. A condition is necessary for a word to pass from one language to another. This condition is not just the connection, coexistence, territorial convergence of two languages, but mutual influence, cooperation and the phenomenon of bilingualism arising on this basis. In history, the Uzbek language has been in contact with sister languages belonging to the Turkic language family, such as Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Uyghur, Karakalpak, Uyghur, Turkmen, and Azerbaijani languages. This relationship continues even now. Thanks to this connection, in many regions of Uzbekistan, people who can speak Uzbek and Kyrgyz, Uzbek and Kazakh, Turkmen and Uzbek, Tatar and Uzbek, Karakalpak and Uzbek in parallel there is a bilingual population. The ability to speak two such genetically related sister languages has existed among the population living in Uzbekistan since ancient times.

The development of international relations, international economic, political, cultural relations and their effects are reflected in the lexicon of the languages of these nations. There are countless studies devoted to the importance and role of such phenomena. However, despite this, the debates and discussions in this regard have not ended. Because linguists have not come to a common and firm conclusion on the issue of word acquisition.

The transfer of words from one language to another is a positive thing. It is also worth noting that just as there is no language whose development is limited only by its internal possibilities, there is no language whose development is based only on external possibilities - borrowing linguistic units from other languages. Acquiring words does not mean acquiring all the words of another language, but rather acquiring the necessary ones from them. That is why word acquisition is one of the external factors of language development.

In fact, the external world is thoroughly sifted through the word, the things-phenomena of the external world that need to be named are "searched" by the word. Because words are collective memory, cultural monument, mirror of people's life. The acquired words are not without these qualities. They are the key to the world of life of this people; in general, learning is the key that opens the way to all knowledge.

It is known that the lexicon and its various layers "get" differently according to their character and acquire a specific linguistic value. This indicates that the lexicon is a complex linguistic level. The interaction of each nation and its language with other nations and their languages is also reflected in the lexicon. Therefore, it is permissible to compare the lexicon of the language to a mirror. Just as a mirror shows the reflection of everything that is directed at it, so the lexicon of language shows all the features of the social and spiritual world. For this reason, every innovation, every change in the social and spiritual world of the society finds its expression first in the structure of the dictionary. In fact, the lexicon reflects all the changes in social life, the traces of the people's historical path. Now, in researching the vocabulary of a particular language, it is necessary to analyze the position and scope of foreign language elements, their specific characteristics from this point of view.

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